

Sold By

Appario Retail Private Ltd
Unit No. 1, Khewat/ Khata No: 373/ 400 Mustatil No 31,
Village Taoru, Tehsil Taoru, District Mewat,
On Bilaspur Taoru Road
Mewat - 122105
Haryana, India

DgBLQZFWZ /-1 of 1 -// std-in-10k

Invoice Number: DEL2-531633

Order ID 404-6585937-0829108

This is a computer generated document

QTY DESCRIPTION

1 **TECNO Spark 7T(Jewel Blue, 4GB RAM, 64GB Storage) 6000 mAh Battery| 48 MP AI Dual Rear Camera**
B096LS7N6Z

Registered Address for
Appario Retail Private Ltd, 1st Floor, UB Plaza, St. Marks Road,, Shantala Nagar, Bangalore - 560001, KARNATAKA, IN

To return an item, visit <http://www.amazon.in/returns>
For more information on your orders, visit <http://www.amazon.in/your-account>

DgBLQZFWZ /-1 of 1 -// std-in-10k/ 0623-13:02/ 0626-01:30

Purchase made on